

FIBRE/MATRIX ADHESION IN THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES: IS TRANSCRYSTALLINITY A KEY?

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SUMMARY: Single fibre pull-out specimens with carbon fibres (AS4, T300, T700, T800) embedded in PEEK or PPS matrix were produced using a hot stage. Transcrystallinity, or the formation of row nucleated crystalline matrix cylindrites, was induced through fibre shearing during matrix recrystallisation, resulting in the formation of a banded crystalline matrix structure. The interfacial shear strength has been evaluated to study the influence of transcrystallinity on fibre/matrix adhesion of thermoplastic composites. Transcrystallinity was found to have little or no positive influence on the interfacial shear strength of CF/PEEK systems, and a negative influence on CF/PPS systems. Under these circumstances, the merit of inducing transcrystallinity in composite systems should be reassessed.

KEYWORDS: transcrystallinity, fibre/matrix interface, matrix morphology, interfacial shear strength, PPS, PEEK, thermoplastic composite

INTRODUCTION

Studies of the region between the fibre and matrix of a composite system, known as an interface or interphase, are of major interest in the determination of composite properties. The strength of a composite is dependent on the properties of its component matrix and reinforcing fibre, but importantly it is also a product of the ability to transfer stress between the fibre and matrix. Therefore an understanding of the interaction between fibre and matrix is essential to evaluation and optimisation of composite properties. Much of the work on semicrystalline thermoplastic composite interfaces has concerned the formation of transcrystalline layers around the reinforcing fibres. These layers are created through closely spaced nucleation on the reinforcing fibre [1], creating cylindrites around the reinforcing fibre. The methods of processing that will induce transcrystalline zones around single fibres has been very well documented, particularly for GF/polypropylene composites [1-2], either with shearing of the fibre or with the fibre undisturbed [3]. However, it was evident in the literature that the effects of the transcrystalline matrix structure on stress transfer mechanisms was not clearly understood.

In the present work, the interfacial shear strengths were studied using single fibre pull-out tests for PEEK and PPS polymer with four different types of carbon fibres, namely AS4, T300, T700 and T800. The single fibre pull-out specimens were produced with and without transcrystalline layers. Effects of transcrystalline and non-transcrystalline matrix structures on pull-out strengths are investigated, and discussed in terms of their importance to bulk composite properties.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TESTING METHOD

A schematic of the single fibre pull-out specimen, containing a carbon fibre (Hercules AS4, or T300, T700 and T800 from Torayca) and a semicrystalline matrix (PEEK or PPS) is shown in Fig. 1. Filaments of PEEK matrix were obtained, separating them from commingled yarn CF/PEEK (supplied by BASF), with a diameter of approximately 30 μm . PPS fibres were obtained by melting PPS powder (supplied by Phillips Petroleum), and spinning filaments of a diameter between 20 μm and 50 μm from the just-molten liquid with a scalpel blade. One matrix filament was placed on one half of a glass slide, with a single carbon fibre attached to the other half with cyanoacrylate adhesive. The two halves of the slide were then placed adjacent to one another, with the carbon fibre placed across and perpendicular to the matrix filament. A glass cover slip was then placed over the fibre and matrix. A Mettler FP82 hot stage, controlled by a Mettler FP90 central processor, was used to heat the specimen to its processing temperature, where the carbon fibre becomes embedded in the matrix which subsequently holds the fibre at its recrystallisation temperature.

Fig. 1: Schematic of specimen for single fibre pull-out test.

Ten specimens of each fibre/matrix system were produced with or without transcrystallinity, respectively. For the CF/PEEK systems, pull-out specimens were heated to 375°C, held for 15 minutes, then cooled at 20°C/min to a recrystallisation temperature of 310°C, creating the normal matrix morphology without transcrystallinity. Specimens with transcrystallinity were produced through slightly pulling the fibre at the beginning of the recrystallisation period. Similarly the CF/PPS pull-out specimens were produced, holding at a melt temperature of 320°C for 10 mins with a recrystallisation temperature of 240°C. Transcrystalline CF/PPS pull-out specimens followed the same processing method, with a slight pulling of the fibre at 250°C during the cooling stage. After cooling the single fibre pull-out specimen to ambient temperature, the fibre was pulled out of its surrounding matrix at a speed of 0.4 mm/min using an Instron 5567 machine with a 2.5N load cell. After testing, the embedded length of the fibre was measured using an image analysis system attached to a Leica DM-RXE microscope. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was calculated as

$$IFSS = \frac{P}{2\pi rl} \quad (1)$$

where P is the maximum load, r the fibre radius and l the embedded fibre length.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The formation of the transcrystalline layer for an AS4/PEEK single fibre pull-out specimen is shown in partly cross-polarised light micrographs (Figs. 2a-c). Upon reaching the recrystallisation temperature of 310°C, the fibre was pulled approximately 15 µm, and a bright band appeared around the carbon fibre (Fig. 2a). The orientation of polymer chains caused by the shearing stress appears to increase the transmissibility of light, giving a whitened region in the transmission light micrograph. The transcrystalline layer then continued to grow (Fig. 2b) with time. Eventually the banded formation of the transcrystalline layer can clearly be identified, as described by Varga and Karger-Kocsis [1] for glass fibre/polypropylene systems. With increased holding time, crystalline structures began to form in the bulk of the PEEK matrix (Fig. 2c). However, in this study the formation of spherulites in the PEEK was restricted by the processing temperature of 375°C (the maximum temperature of the Mettler FP82 hot stage). Rather than the near-spherical crystalline spherulites traditionally associated with semi-crystalline polymers, the PEEK forms into highly axial, sheaf-like crystallites. Jar et al [5] found that PEEK processed at a temperature less than 395°C formed a densely nucleated matrix, and subsequently proposed that the formation of 1-2 µm sheaves of PEEK results from a melting temperature lower than 395°C, above which the self-seeding effect of PEEK matrix is removed. The cross-polarised light micrograph of the transcrystalline AS4/PEEK pull-out specimen shown in Fig. 3a clearly illustrates a prominent banded structure. However, the size of the transcrystalline layer is quite small compared to equivalent structures formed in glass fibre/polypropylene systems [1]. It is presumed that the low processing temperature of the specimen (375°C) promotes the fast formation of crystalline structures in the bulk matrix, limiting the size of growth of the transcrystalline layer.

A similar process for the formation of the transcrystalline layer for a T800/PPS single fibre pull-out specimen is shown in Figs. 2d-f. The bright band surrounding the carbon fibre after shearing (Fig. 2d) is clearer in PPS than the PEEK, due either to the darker colour of the PPS matrix or a more ordered molecular chain arrangement on shearing. Spherulites developing in the PPS matrix (Fig. 2f) are randomly nucleated ball-shaped formations, rather than the sheaf formation found in the AS4/PEEK specimens. The cross-polarised light micrograph in Fig. 3b clearly illustrates the transcrystalline layer in T800/PPS pull-out specimens. However, the transcrystalline zone in T800/PPS is less clear than the equivalent PEEK structure after processing.

*Fig. 2: Growth of transcrystalline layer:
(a) - (c) for AS4/PEEK, and (d) - (f) for T800/PPS.*

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: Cross-polarised micrograph of transcrystalline pull-out specimens: (a) AS4/PEEK and (b) T800/PSS.

Fig. 4: Interfacial shear strength of different carbon fibres with PEEK.

The interfacial shear strengths (IFSS) of AS4, T300, T700 and T800 carbon fibres embedded in PEEK matrix with and without transcrystallinity are shown in Fig. 4. It should be noted that comparisons between specimens of different fibre types may not be valid, as an adequate control could not be maintained over variables such as humidity between fibre groups. Testing of transcrystalline and non-transcrystalline specimens was alternated for each fibre group, and therefore only comparisons between the transcrystalline and non-transcrystalline specimens should be made. The effect of transcrystallinity on the IFSS of the embedded fibre is only apparent in the AS4 fibre specimens, with transcrystalline specimens showing a higher IFSS than non-transcrystalline specimens. There appears to be some similar influence in T300 fibre specimens, but this is not significant enough to draw conclusive results. Also, while on average the transcrystalline T700 and T800 specimens had higher IFSS than the non-transcrystalline specimens, the scatter of each shows that no inference can be drawn from these results. The influence of different fibre type should also be considered. Both the AS4 and T700 are pitch-based carbon fibres, and have a very smooth fibre surface. T300 and T800 fibres, on the other hand, are PAN-based and have a ribbed surface. However, the above aspects do not favour one carbon fibre type with respect to the pull-out behaviour of transcrystalline and non-transcrystalline specimens. It is noted that AS4 fibre and T300 fibres are low in modulus compared to T700 and T800 fibres. Also, the radius of AS4 and T300 fibres, at 7 μm each, gives a higher surface area than the T700 fibre (6 μm) or T800 fibre (5 μm).

The IFSS for AS4, T300, T700 and T800 carbon fibres embedded in PPS matrix with and without transcrystallinity are shown in Fig. 5. It should again be stressed that comparisons between the IFSS of different fibre types may be invalid. However there is an overall trend to

Fig. 5: Interfacial shear strength of different carbon fibres with PPS.

lower IFSS with transcrystalline formations in all fibre types. This suggests that transcrystalline formations of PPS around carbon fibres do not improve IFSS. Studies by Moon [4] suggest that differing levels of contraction stress exist around the fibre with different crystalline polymer formations. The transcrystalline zone, which forms almost immediately around the fibre, will impose a different constraint condition around the fibre to a randomly nucleated matrix, creating different levels of contraction stresses. Comparing the influence of contraction stresses on CF/PPS with CF/PEEK specimens is difficult, due to the markedly different formation of crystal structure in the PEEK matrix with the chosen processing conditions. Therefore, it not possible to verify the influence of this mechanism with the current data.

It is fair to state, given the apparent influence of transcrystalline formations on the stress transfer mechanism of model single fibre composites, the influence of transcrystallinity on the properties of bulk composites may be limited. Furthermore, special processing conditions may be required to induce transcrystallinity in bulk composites. Specifically, the requirement of inducing relative shear between fibre and matrix, when fibres in a bulk composite are very closely packed, may be very difficult to achieve, and add substantially to the processing costs, without tangible benefits. Under this circumstance, more positive properties of transcrystalline matrix structures will be required to justify a very specialised processing methodology.

CONCLUSION

The formation of transcrystalline zones around carbon fibres has been studied in PEEK and PPS matrices, and the interfacial shear strengths (IFSS) of AS4, T300, T700 and T800 carbon fibres have been evaluated for PEEK and PPS matrix, with and without transcrystallinity. The formation of the transcrystalline zone, which results from a dense concentration of nucleation sites near or along the carbon fibre surface after pulling, was shown to have a banded formation in both the PEEK and PPS matrices, being similar to GF/PP systems shown in previous studies. Pull-out testing of carbon fibres from PEEK and PPS matrices has shown that transcrystallinity is not significant in improving IFSS. In fact, pull-out specimens for PPS appear to have decreased in IFSS as a result of the presence of transcrystallinity. Special processing conditions of temperature and holding time had to be adopted to form transcrystalline zones in these model single fibre composites, and this would probably involve additional expense in processing. Also, the likelihood of transcrystalline zone formation in bulk composites is low, as relative shear may be needed between the reinforcing fibre and its surrounding matrix during processing.

In conclusion, attention to the matrix morphology at the fibre interface does not appear to be rewarded with increased interfacial shear performance, which is critical to the overall mechanical performance of the bulk composite. Further work would need to be conducted to identify more positive aspects of transcrystalline formations, before transcrystallinity is adopted as a matrix microstructure to improve the composite performance.

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